

HIGH-TEMPERATURE DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR AND
MICROSTRUCTURAL INVESTIGATION OF SILICON CARBIDE PARTICULATE
REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Microstructure and deformation behaviour of a SiC particulate reinforced 6061 Al composite at high temperature have been investigated. The samples of both composite and matrix alloy were thermal cycled in air between 35 and 350°C up to 6×10^3 cycles. In order to compare the effect of thermal fatigue and isothermal exposure at high temperature on the strength of composite, the samples were aged isothermally at 350°C for different ageing times. Transmission electron microscopy was undertaken to examine the microstructural changes occurring during thermal fatigue and high temperature exposure. It was found that no degradation occurred at the interface between the SiC particles and Al matrix in the samples subjected to thermal fatigue up to 6×10^3 cycles but heavy dislocation density was observed in the region adjacent to particle matrix interface in these samples. The results also showed that strength of the composite did not change significantly after thermal cycling.

Hot working behaviour of composite was studied by uniaxial hot compression at constant straining rates from 0.001 to 1 s^{-1} in the temperature range 200 to 500°C. True stress-true strain curves showed that material exhibited flow behaviour corresponding to dynamic recovery in which flow stress rises rapidly to a maximum at low strains and then approaches a steady-state value. The composite displayed nonlinear strain rate sensitivity as well as two stages of activation energy of deformation under high temperature deformation conditions.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Matrix; Aluminium; High Temperature Deformation/Thermal Fatigue.

1. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous ceramic material reinforced Al composites have attracted the attention of many researchers and manufacturers in recent years because of their unique combination of specific strength and high modulus^{1,2}. By comparing with continuous fibre reinforced composites, whisker and particulate reinforced composites have the advantages of lower cost, easier fabricating process, better workability and more homogenous properties¹⁻³. Considerable work on creep and high temperature properties has been done on whisker reinforced composites but not much attention has been paid on the thermomechanical behaviour of the particulate reinforced composites, especially effects of size, volume and shape of hard ceramic particulates on the recovery and recrystallization of two-phase composites¹⁻⁴. Also, influence of thermal environments such as thermal cycling and isothermal exposure on the bonding of the particles and matrix in such composites have not been studied in detail.

In the present study, thermal fatigue resistance and high temperature mechanical behaviour of silicon carbide particulate reinforced 6061 aluminium composite have been investigated by thermal cycling and isothermal hot compression. TEM, SEM and optical microscopy were carried out to study the structural changes after thermal cycling and hot compression.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The material used for this work was 6061 aluminium with 10 vol. percent SiC particulates supplied by Comalco Research Centre and Hindustan Aeronautics Ltd. The composite was fabricated first by casting and then rolled into plate (6.1mm thick and 76mm wide) or extruded into bar (19mm dia.) followed by solution treatment at 535°C for one hour. Samples were taken from parallel to direction of extrusion.

Thermal cycling experiments were performed in air between 35 and 350°C up to 6000 cycles. The solenoids controlled by computer were used to pull the sample out from the furnace when the sample needed cooling and pushed in the hot zone when it was heated up. The compressed air was blown on the sample as soon as it was withdrawn from the furnace. One thermal cycle needed 140 seconds which was comprised of 60 seconds for

heating and 80 seconds for cooling down. The temperature and the number of cycles were monitored by the computer.

To compare the effect of thermal cycling and isothermal exposure at high temperature on the properties of the composite, the samples were aged at 350°C up to 18 hours. Exposure time was chosen to be same as the heating time of any definite number of cycles. For instance, 200 thermal cycles needed heating time of 3.5 hours. Therefore the sample exposed at 350°C for 3.5 hours would be compared with the sample thermal cycled 200 times, and so on.

Isothermal hot compression testing was carried out on a Dartec Servo-Hydraulic testing machine modified for hot compression under constant straining rate. All tests were carried out in air between 200 and 500°C. The samples were held at the testing temperature for 5 minutes prior to compression and then given reduction of 60% at strain rates ranging from 0.001 to 1 s⁻¹. The samples were quenched immediately after deformation for microstructural investigation.

The microstructure was examined with the aid of either optical microscopy or transmission electron microscopy (TEM). TEM specimens were prepared using a Struer Tenupol jet polishing system operating at 30 V, using a polishing solution of 20% HNO₃ in methanol at a temperature of -30°C. Fracture surfaces were observed using a scanning electron microscope.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 is a typical microstructure of an extruded SiC/A1 particulate composite. It can be seen that particulates are not uniformly distributed in the matrix. SiC particles have irregular shape and rough surface with varying sizes ranging from 1 to 5 μm. Some of the particulate free zones can be easily seen and the presence of such regions can influence the mechanical behaviour of composite both at ambient and high temperatures. Fig. 2 shows the TEM micrograph of as - received composite in which high dislocation density in the vicinity of SiC particles can be noticed. It seems that a large number of dislocations were generated either by deformation during fabricating processes and/or as a result of strain generated due to mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficients between

SiC and aluminium matrix.

FIGURE 1. Heterogeneous distribution of SiC as well as particle morphology (6061 Al / 10% SiC, x 1500).

FIGURE 2. A high density of dislocation in the vicinity of SiC particles.

The transmission electron micrograph of reinforced alloy which has been thermal cycled for 2000 times is shown in Fig. 3. Several features can be observed in this micrograph. Firstly, there was no obvious matrix reaction with SiC and secondly no interface degradation was detected i.e. no decohesion at particle/matrix interface was observed. In comparison to as - received material, the thermal cycled composite showed much denser dislocation network adjacent to SiC/Al interface. Finally, coarse precipitate particles presumably of Mg_2Si were present in the matrix after thermal cycling.

Thermal cycling confirmed that dislocations were generated around corners of the SiC reinforcement⁵. As can be seen in Fig. 4 that higher dislocation density was associated with corners of the SiC particles rather than with the rest of the matrix. Precipitates were seen along grain boundaries and the particles were associated with pinning the dislocations as found in the as - received material. However, as the number of thermal cycles increased, fine precipitates continuously precipitated on the dislocations in the (100) direction, giving the structure a streaked look, (Figs. 3 and 5). Arsenaault et al have also reported the precipitation on thermally generated dislocations as well as presence of denser dislocation network at the interface on cooling from the annealing temperature⁶.

Theoretically, difference of thermal expansion coefficients between SiC and Al will

FIGURE 3. High dislocation density around corner of SiC particle and precipitates. Fine precipitates give the structure a streaked look. (Thermal cycled for 2000 cycles, 6061 Al / 10% SiC, x 10000).

FIGURE 4. Heavily dislocated structure adjacent to the edge of a SiC particle. (Thermal cycled for 500 cycles, 6061 Al / 10% SiC, x 19500).

generate shearing and tensile stresses at the interface during thermal cycling. These stresses could be high enough to break the bonding between particle and matrix and leave voids and cracks at the interface. However, voids or cracks were not observed in any of the particulate reinforced samples after thermal cycling in the present work although debonding after thermal cycling has been reported in fibre-reinforced composite⁷. These results suggest that level of stresses at interface in particulate - reinforced material seems

to be of much lower magnitude causing no damage or debonding compared to composite with fibre reinforcement. Also, it is likely that stress concentration at the interface can be easily accommodated around particulates compared to fibres, resulting the absence of voids or cracks in particulate reinforced material.

FIGURE 5. Heavily dislocated structure with aacicular precipitates in the (100) direction. (Thermal cycled 2000 cycles, 6061 Al / 10% SiC, x 15000)

FIGURE 6. Tensile test curves of the composite and matrix alloy after thermal cycling and isothermal exposure. (a. Thermal cycled composites, 10^3 cycles. b. Isothermal aged composite, 17.5 hours. c. Thermal cycled 6061 Al matrix alloy, 10^3 cycles).

Fig. 6 shows the results of tensile tests conducted at room temperature on samples of composite and matrix alloy after thermal cycling and isothermal ageing. Several observations can be made from these results: firstly, the strength of reinforced alloy was much higher than that of the matrix alloy, but the composite showed lower tensile ductility; secondly, samples in both thermal cycled and isothermal aged conditions exhibited almost similar strength and finally, the ductility of composite remained almost unchanged after thermal cycling and isothermal ageing suggesting that such thermal treatments did not deteriorate the strength and/or ductility of particulate reinforced SiC/Al composite.

The effect of thermal cycling and isothermal ageing on the strength of the composite and matrix alloy is shown in Fig. 7. The results showed that as the number of thermal cycles

increased, the strength of reinforced alloy did not change significantly. It was also found that there was hardly any observable difference in strength either after thermal cycling or in isothermally aged samples. It is generally considered that repeated heating and cooling

FIGURE 7. Tensile strength of the composite and matrix alloy at room temperature after thermal cycling and isothermal ageing.

FIGURE 8. Fracture surface of tensile tested composite after thermal cycling, 1000 cycles between 35 and 350°C.

(thermal fatigue) could cause decohesion between particles and matrix due to development of high tensile and shearing stresses at the particle/matrix interface and such decohesion at interface could give rise to failure of reinforced material at much lower stress levels. However, the results of the present study indicate that strength remained almost unchanged when the number of thermal cycles were increased. It can be seen from the micrograph of reinforced alloy (Figs. 1 and 5) that SiC particles, which were present with irregular shapes and rough surfaces, tend to grip the matrix firmly resulting in fairly strong bonding between particle and matrix. Fig. 8 shows the fractograph of composite sample subjected thermal cycling up to 10^3 times. At the fracture surface, it was very difficult to identify a significant population of SiC particles and the fracture was mainly caused by matrix failure rather than debonding of the particles and matrix. These observations further support the idea that bonding is quite strong in the present composite resulting in strength which did not change significantly even after large numbers of thermal cycles.

There can be several reasons for good bonding between SiC particle and matrix. Firstly, irregular shape and rough surfaces of the particles are suitable for good mechanical bonding. It has been reported that mechanical bonding could provide high bonding strength which could not be achieved by chemical bonding alone. Good mechanical bonding could improve bonding strength significantly⁸ and it is understandable that mechanical gripping of the SiC particles by the matrix is sufficient to cause an effective reinforcement. Secondly, diffusion controlled strengthening of interface is also an important factor. It was found that dislocation not only existed in the Al matrix, but were present also in the reinforcement and these dislocations might provide channels for Al atoms diffusion into reinforcing materials. It has been suggested that this process could strengthen the bonding in composite⁹ and it is envisaged that both these phenomena occurred in the present composite.

FIGURE 9. Influence of temperature on true stress vs. true strain for the composite after hot compression at a strain rate of 0.1 s^{-1} .

FIGURE 10. Influence of strain rate on true stress vs. true strain derived from hot compression data at 400°C .

The true stress - true strain curves obtained at various strain rates and temperatures are shown in Figs. 9 and 10 respectively. The shape of these curves is typical of the form expected when dynamic recovery occurs; that is, the flow stress rises sharply to a maximum and then approaches a steady-state value. It can be seen that either increasing strain rate or decreasing temperature resulted in an increase in flow stress. The flow stress increased by one order of magnitude when the test temperature was decreased from

500 to 400°C. The change in temperature from 400 to 300°C resulted in three order of magnitude increase in steady state flow stress. The reason for the behaviour can be explained as follows. TEM of sample deformed at 500°C, Fig. 11 shows that a fine substructure evolved during deformation with fine precipitates in the matrix pinning the

FIGURE 11. Fine structure with dislocations pinned by precipitates and grain boundaries. Compressed at 500°C to a strain of 0.6 at the strain rate of 0.1 s (x 10500, 6061 Al / 10% SiC).

FIGURE 12. Transmission electron micrograph of a sample deformed to a strain of 0.6 at 400°C in compression and water quenched: Fine dislocation structure within the grains can be seen.

boundaries and dislocations. Large SiC particulates were not able to hinder the motion of dislocations due to their size as reported elsewhere. It can be seen from Fig. 12 that a sample deformed at 400°C exhibited a much finer dislocation substructure compared to one strained at 500°C to equivalent strain and such this finer substructure can be responsible for higher flow stress at the lower temperature. Thus it is suggested that it would be most desirable to hot work such materials around 500°C, while 400°C being the lower limit for hot working.

A plot of $\ln \sigma_0$ vs $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ is shown in Fig. 13. The slope of this curve will give the strain rate sensitivity of flow stress, m . The value of m was evaluated to be 0.11 which is quite small for 10% SiC/Al composite, suggesting that the material will be difficult to be formed i.e. as lower m generally leads to lower ductility in metals and alloys. It should be mentioned that the internal stresses which are found in composites contribute to enhancing the plastic flow in the direction of the externally applied stress¹⁰. However, at

large strains since the magnitude of the applied stress is much higher than the internal stress, the strain rate sensitivity exponent can be low in such situations.

FIGURE 13. Plot of $\ln \sigma_0$ vs. $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ data for the 6061 Al / 10% SiC. The slope of the curve gives the strain rate sensitivity (m).

FIGURE 14. Plot of $\ln \sigma_0$ vs. $1/T$ for the 6061 Al / 10% SiC. Activation energy of deformation (Q) can be evaluated from the slope.

The activation energy of deformation (Q) was computed from the flow stress vs deformation temperature data at a strain rate of $0.1 s^{-1}$, Fig. 14. The results showed that the deformation process is complex to be characterized by a single activation energy over the temperature range studied. The plot of $\ln \sigma_0$ vs $1/T$ exhibited nonlinear behaviour suggesting that the deformation process be characterized by two activation energies. Between 500 and $300^\circ C$, the activation energy was evaluated to be 299 KJ/mole whilst 158 KJ/mole was found between 300 and $200^\circ C$. These results suggest that the material responded differently once it reaches $300^\circ C$. In contrast, the activation energy for self-diffusion of aluminium is only 150 KJ/mole¹¹. Therefore the activation energy of 158 KJ/mole obtained for SiC/Al composite between 200 and $300^\circ C$ is very close to that of 150 KJ/mole suggesting that the rate controlling step of deformation at initial stages is diffusion controlled. Recent work by Pickens et al in torsion suggests that there can be more than one activation energy for deformation in reinforced SiC/Al composites¹².

The activation energy of 229 KJ/mole found in this work is quite high. Nieh et al have

also reported activation energy of approximately 390 KJ/mole for 20% SiC/Al material tested in creep¹³. It should be mentioned that the activation energies of 229 KJ/mole obtained between 400 and 500°C in this study and that of Nieh et al are quite high. Existing theories based on dislocation climb predict that the temperature dependence can be the same as that for either bulk or pipe diffusion depending which process prevails¹⁴. Neither process can properly account for the high activation energies observed in either study. The discrepancies suggest that either a major modification of the current theories is required or an entirely new theoretical approach will be necessary.

It should, however, be mentioned that particulate reinforced composites seem to have similar behaviour as conventional oxide dispersion strengthened aluminium alloys¹⁵. In that they exhibit low strain rate sensitivity and a high apparent activation energy of deformation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. No degradation at SiC/Al interface was observed after thermal fatigue or/and high temperature exposure in reinforced alloy.
2. It was found that there was hardly any observable difference in strength of reinforced alloy either after thermal cycling or isothermal ageing. Also as the number of thermal cycles increased the strength of composite did not change significantly.
3. The flow behaviour of SiC/Al composite at high temperatures was typical of the materials which show dynamic recovery. The composite exhibited low strain rate sensitivity (m). The change in temperature from 400 to 300°C resulted in three order of magnitude increase in steady state flow stress whilst the flow stress increased by one order of magnitude when the test temperature was decreased from 500 to 400°C.
4. The material displayed two activation energy of deformation values. A low value of 158 KJ/mole in the temperature range 200 - 300°C and 229 KJ/mole between 300 - 500°C.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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